

Architectural, Cultural and Historical game-based modelling approach through integrating ChoiCo and GeoGebra

Type of contribution: Workshop

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Introduction

This workshop paper explores a novel, gamified approach to architectural mathematical modelling, building upon existing research that integrates architecture and mathematics education. Utilizing the robust mathematical foundation of GeoGebra¹ and the engaging, choice-driven world of the simulation gaming platform, ChoiCo², the proposed game offers a multifaceted learning experience. Users embark on a virtual tour of Linz, Austria, uncovering its architectural, historical, and cultural landmarks while strategically navigating challenges to maintain their in-game performance. This integration seamlessly redirects users to GeoGebra applets throughout the gameplay, enabling them to apply architectural mathematical modelling concepts inspired by their virtual exploration. Developed by the TransEET³ Community of Interest “AR Gaming in STEM Education”, this innovative approach, aligns with the STEAM + X framework, promoting transdisciplinary learning through the integration of various disciplines. Targeting first-year architectural students, the game fosters exploration of urban architecture, city culture, and history, while offering practical application of architectural mathematical modelling. Additionally, augmented reality (AR) integration with GeoGebra allows users to visualize their models in the real world, further enriching the engagement. This iterative design process, drawing upon the "Flow of Rapid Prototyping" concept (Jensen, et al., 2016), encourages creativity, personalization, and user ownership, aiming to contribute to a dynamic and engaging learning experience.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework behind the proposed game-based learning activity is grounded in several theoretical frameworks that underpin the pedagogical and cognitive benefits of it. The basis of the rationale of this proposal is rooted in a constructionist approach where learning is perceived as an active process where individuals construct knowledge and meaning through their experiences and interactions with the environment (Grizioti & Kynigos, 2021). By engaging students in hands-on activities such as modelling real life architectural designs in GeoGebra and making decisions in ChoiCo, the activity aligns with constructionist principles. Also, drawing from theories of

¹ <https://www.geogebra.org/>

² <http://etl.ppp.uoa.gr/choico/>

³ Transforming Education with Emerging Technologies, Project No. 101078875, <https://transeet.eu/>

gamification (Christopoulos & Mystakidis, 2023), the activity leverages game elements and mechanics to enhance engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. By incorporating elements such as rewards, feedback, and progression pathways, the activity aims to make learning mathematics and architectural concepts more enjoyable and immersive for students. Furthermore, our game design aligns with situated learning theory (Wenger, 2022) by contextualizing learning within the domain of architectural design, providing students with meaningful connections between theoretical concepts and real-world applications. This approach further integrates the STEAM + X framework (El Bedewy & Lavicza, 2023), promoting transdisciplinary learning and cultural awareness through exploration. By fostering problem-solving skills and strategies (Polya, 2004), this game-based learning activity aims to create a dynamic and engaging learning experience for students, emphasizing in understanding the problem, devising a plan, and employing continuous backward and forward thinking to explore all options and make informed decisions. This game's design also allows for its accessibility across various devices, including computers, laptops, and mobile devices, making it adaptable to diverse learning environments.

Methodology

This paper employs design-based research (DBR) methodology (Cobb et al., 2003) to iteratively develop and refine the proposed game-based learning activity. In the first cycle, users will navigate a virtual representation of Linz, Austria, engaging with the initial game design and providing feedback through various methods. Leveraging a rapid prototyping approach within DBR (Jensen et al., 2016), users will be able to create their own modified versions of the game, facilitating user-driven design and customization. These user-created prototypes will be tested in successive cycles, informing further refinements to the overall game design. This cyclical process aligns perfectly with the core principle of DBR - adapting the design to meet learning objectives and user needs - ensuring the game continuously improves and aligns with user preferences and educational goals. A key advantage is that both software tools are user modifiable. Additionally, the rapid prototyping approach allows for the regeneration of learning materials in subsequent game versions. User-created artifacts can be exchanged and redesigned, fostering collaboration and contributing to the continuous improvement of the game-based learning experience.

Workshop Structure

In this paper we intend to present this game in a workshop setting, introducing the participants to the learning objective of the game and providing clear instructions on how to engage with it. Our focus is on demonstrating the mathematical modelling of a simple architecture using GeoGebra software. Through this, we aim to equip all participants with fundamental skills in utilizing GeoGebra's functions and equations. Following this introduction, we will delve into the ChoiCo interface, emphasizing the concept of rapid prototyping. Participants will customize and co-create game elements within the ChoiCo platform, gaining hands-on experience with game design principles and personalized learning. This aligns with emerging trends in user-driven design and collaborative learning environments. For instance, in group settings, each group will be encouraged to develop a unique game version incorporating their own mathematical modelling images and augmented reality representations of their architectural designs. This new game version allows participants to upload

mathematical modelling images and augmented reality (AR) representations of their architectural designs directly from GeoGebra into the updated ChoiCo game. They can further personalize the experience by modifying the city tour and incorporating new learning materials, fostering iterative game development. In the coming part we will highlight the design of the game flow.

The Game Design

The initial phase of the game developed using ChoiCo. ChoiCo games are designed to depict this complexity through a structured system comprising choices, consequences, fields, rules, and relationships (Grizioti & Kynigos, 2021). Players navigate through diverse map-like areas, where their decisions directly impact the numerical outcomes within the game's fields (Figure 1c). These fields embody key principles, such as Knowledge, Money, Energy and Experience. The game's design empowers users with a range of variables that they must carefully balance as they embark on a city tour, exploring various landmarks that influence these variables. This tour entails visiting interesting architectural landmarks such as Ars Electronica Museum and Old Cathedral, each with its potential to alter the values of these variables (Figure 1a). These landmarks were selected due to the significant architectural, cultural and historical interest they possess, while other landmarks such as the Botanical Garden & Cafe also included, in order to create a “real-life” atmosphere for users where they have to prioritize their moves and decisions in the game. Moreover, certain landmarks within the game become accessible at specific points based on the variable’s values. For instance, an ATM location may appear when users run low on funds, providing them with an opportunity to replenish their money reserves. Similarly, the addition of a landmark café serves to replenish users' energy levels in case they run out during the city tour.

Figure 1: Screenshots from ChoiCo, from left to right: (a) the landmarks on Linz map (b) inner layers of the game (c) the game variables

Upon reaching certain thresholds in their "knowledge" and "experience," players unknowingly unlock access to deeper levels of the game (Figure 1b). These hidden layers reveal new landmarks linked to GeoGebra applets, enabling them to mathematically model the city's architecture. The applets provide instructional materials, AR integration (Figure 2a), examples of similar models (Figure 2b), and site maps (Figure 2c) to support their modeling efforts.

Figure 2: Screenshots from GeoGebra applets displaying Ars Electronica modelling from left to right: in GeoGebra & AR mode, and the top and side view of Architecture

Throughout gameplay, users receive notifications guiding them to maintain balanced scores and progress towards higher knowledge levels, unlocking advanced modeling features within GeoGebra applets. Upon completing their architectural models, users are prompted to share the applet links and upload their corresponding AR images directly into the editable ChoiCo data table. These contributions allow users to download their personalized, modified versions of the game.

Discussion

By integrating elements from architecture, mathematics, history, and culture, the proposed game offers a multifaceted learning experience. Through engaging with these aspects, users are encouraged to develop critical thinking, inquiry, and problem-solving skills. The proposed game holds promise for continued refinement and development. Future development will focus on two key areas: iterative development and expanding the game's scope. Through ongoing user feedback and evaluations, the game will be refined to ensure it remains relevant, engaging, and effective in achieving its educational goals. Additionally, incorporating diverse urban environments will broaden the exploration of architectural styles, historical contexts, and cultural influences. Furthermore, future research will assess the game's long-term impact on students' learning outcomes, academic performance, and interdisciplinary learning across various disciplines. In conclusion, this game showcases the potential of gamification and immersive experiences to enhance holistic learning and skill development within the 21st-century educational landscape. We believe this project, as it continues to evolve, can contribute significantly to the advancement of educational practices and pedagogical approaches.

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